

SUBSTITUTION IN THE BENZOPYRONE SERIES. PART II*.
SULPHONATION OF COUMARIN DERIVATIVES

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The sulphonation of coumarin, 6-nitrocoumarin, 7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin and its methyl ether, and 7-hydroxy-6-carboxy-4-methylcoumarin and its methyl ester with chlorosulphonic acid have been described. The structures of the sulphonated products have also been established.

During the work on the substitution reactions of benzopyrones, in this laboratory, the sulphonation of a number of coumarin derivatives has been investigated. From the literature (Suter, "The Organic Chemistry of Sulphur", Wiley, New York, p. 458) very little systematic work appears to have been done on the subject. The first attempt at sulphonation of coumarin was made by Perkin (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1871, 24, 49; 1875, 28, 14) who obtained mono- and di-sulphonic acids which were later on shown by Sen and Chakravarti (this *Journal*, 1928, 5, 433) to be the coumarin-6- and -6:8-disulphonic acids. The same authors also obtained the 8-sulphonic acid by the sulphonation of 6-nitrocoumarin. A few other coumarin derivatives were sulphonated (Krüger, *Ber.*, 1923, 56B, 480), but the structure of the sulphonated products had not been established.

In the present investigation, chlorosulphonic acid was used as the sulphonating agent, when, in addition to the sulphonic acids, the sulphonyl chlorides were also obtained in some cases. The sulphonic acids were identified (*vide Experimental*). The sulphonyl chlorides could be easily hydrolysed with water to the corresponding sulphonic acids and were also obtained by heating the sodium sulphonates with excess of chlorosulphonic acid. This interconversion showed that the sulphonic acid and the sulphonyl chloride groups had entered the coumarin nucleus in the same positions. Sulphonamides or sulphanylides were prepared to characterise the sulphonyl chlorides.

Table I describes the experimental conditions under which the different coumarin derivatives were sulphonated.

Attempts to obtain known compounds from (I) or (III) by nitration, bromination, hydrolysis and alkali fusion were unsuccessful. Hence, the positions of the sulphonic acid groups in (I) and (III) were proved by oxidation of their sodium salts with permanganate in alkaline medium, as described by Sen and Chakravarti (*loc. cit.*), when 5-sulphosalicylic acid was obtained in both the cases. No tri-substituted products could be obtained by the sulphonation of coumarin even under vigorous conditions of experiment.

The sulphonation of 6-nitrocoumarin occurred with difficulty, and even under drastic experimental conditions, only mono-sulphonated products, (V) and (VI), were obtained. The structure of (V) was proved by oxidising its sodium salt with alkaline permanganate, when 5-nitrosalicylic acid was obtained, showing that the sulphonation had taken place in the 3-position.

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TABLE I

Substance.	Moles of chloro-sulphonic acid.	Temp.	Period of heating.	Product of sulphonation.
Coumarin (C)*	2	100°	2 hrs.	(I) -6-sulphonic acid ; (II) -6-sulphonyl chloride
	6	130-40°	3	(III) -3 : 6-disulphonic acid ; (IV) -3 : 6-disulphonyl chloride
6-Nitro-C	10	"	4	(V) -3-sulphonic acid ; (VI) -3-sulphonyl chloride
7-Hydroxy-4-methyl-C	4	100°	2	(VII) -6-sulphonic acid ; (VIII) -6-sulphonyl chloride
	4	130-40°	4	(IX) -6 : 8-disulphonic acid
	8	140°	4	(X) -3 : 6 : 8-trisulphonic acid
7-Hydroxy-3 : 6-dibromo-4-methyl-C	10	100°	2	(XI) -8-sulphonic acid
7-Hydroxy-3 : 8-dibromo-4-methyl-C	7.5	"	2	(XII) -6-sulphonic acid ; (XIII) -6-sulphonyl chloride
7-Methoxy-4-methyl-C	4.3	"	2	(XIV) -6-sulphonic acid ; (XV) -6-sulphonyl chloride
	8 (in dry CHCl ₃)	60°	3	(XVI) -3 : 6-disulphonic acid ; (XVII) -3 : 6-disulphonyl chloride
7-Methoxy-3-bromo-4-methyl-C	4	100°	2	(XVIII) -6-sulphonic acid ; (XIX) -6-sulphonyl chloride
7-Hydroxy-6-carbomethoxy-4-methyl-C	1	60° (in dry CHCl ₃)	2	(XX) -7-hydroxy-6-carboxy-4-methyl-coumarin-8-sulphonic acid + unchanged substance.
7-Hydroxy-6-carboxy-4-methyl-C	4	100°	2	(XXI) -3 : 8-disulphonic acid.

* 'C' stands for 'coumarin'.

In order to prove the structure of (VII) the hydrolysis, nitration, alkali fusion, oxidation and methylation of its sodium salt were attempted, but no pure product could be isolated in any case. Demethylation of (XIV) to obtain (VII) was also unsuccessful. Bromination of the sodium salt of (VII) with even one mole of bromine in acetic acid medium at room temperature afforded 7-hydroxy-3 : 6 : 8-tribromo-4-methylcoumarin. A similar observation has been made by Dalvi and Sethna (this *Journal*, 1949, 26, 359).

As (VIII) could be easily hydrolysed to yield (VII), attempts were made to establish the structure of (VIII). It has been observed (Suter, *loc. cit.*, p. 512) that sulphonyl chlorides, in general, are stable towards halogenation, and the same can be effected without modifying the sulphonyl chloride group. Hence, the bromination of (VIII) was carried out with 2 moles of bromine in acetic acid when a dibromosulphonyl chloride was obtained. Attempts were therefore made to prepare a dibromosulphonyl chloride by sulphonation of the two known dibromo derivatives of 7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin (Dalvi *et al.*, *loc. cit.*). 7-Hydroxy-3 : 6-dibromo-4-methylcoumarin, when heated with an excess of chlorosulphonic acid, did not furnish any sulphonyl chloride, but only the 8-sulphonic acid which on bromination yielded 7-hydroxy-3 : 6 : 8-tribromo-4-methylcoumarin, showing the position of the sulphonic acid group in (XI). Sulphonation of 7-hydroxy-3 : 8-dibromo-4-methylcoumarin, on the other hand, afforded a sulphonyl chloride (XIII) and a sulphonic acid which on bromination yielded

7-hydroxy-3:6:8-tribromo-4-methylcoumarin, thus indicating that the sulphonic acid group had entered the 6-position. The sulphonyl chloride (XIII) could be easily hydrolysed to (XII), identical with that obtained by the bromination of (VIII). Thus, (VII) and (VIII) are shown to be the 6-substituted products of 7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin.

Attempts to establish the constitution of the disulphonic acid (IX) by hydrolysis, oxidation, nitration, etc. proved fruitless. It was assigned the structure 7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin-6:8-disulphonic acid from analogy with other 7-hydroxycoumarins, wherein, if the 6-position was blocked, the 8-position was found to be attacked first in preference to 3-position. No definite proof could be obtained about the structure of the trisulphonic acid (X). It was, however, assigned the structure 7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin-3:6:8-trisulphonic acid. No di- or tri-sulphonyl chlorides of 7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin could be obtained even by heating the sodium salts of the di-(IX) and tri-(X) sulphonic acids with excess of chlorosulphonic acid.

The chlorosulphonylation of 7-methoxy-4-methylcoumarin first afforded the 6-sulphonyl chloride (XV) and the 6-sulphonic acid (XIV). The hydrolysis and nitration of the latter failed to furnish any definite products. The bromination of its sodium salt in acetic acid gave only 7-methoxy-3:6-dibromo-4-methylcoumarin. However, the structure of (XIV) was proved by the oxidation of its sodium salt with permanganate in alkaline medium, when 2-hydroxy-4-methoxy-5-sulphobenzoic acid was obtained. The position of the sulphonic acid group in the latter was proved by its bromination, when 2-hydroxy-4-methoxy-5-bromobenzoic acid (Rice, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 48, 3129) was isolated, the constitution of which was confirmed by preparation of its methyl ester and by its decarboxylation to 4-bromoresorcinol-3-methyl ether. As a point of interest, β -resorcylic acid was sulphonated and the structure of the sulphonated product was proved to be 2:4-dihydroxy-5-sulphobenzoic acid.

The sulphonyl chloride (XV) on bromination afforded 7-methoxy-3-bromo-4-methylcoumarin-6-sulphonyl chloride, also synthesised by the chlorosulphonylation of 7-methoxy-3-bromo-4-methylcoumarin, when (XVIII) and (XIX) were obtained.

The disulphonated products (XVI) and (XVII) were proved to be the -3:6-disubstituted compounds of 7-methoxy-4-methylcoumarin. The structure of (XVI) was proved by brominating it when the known 7-methoxy-3:6-dibromo-4-methylcoumarin was obtained. The sulphonation of 7-methoxy-4-methylcoumarin with an excess of chlorosulphonic acid at 130°-140° furnished a trisulphonic acid which gave an intense violet coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride, showing that demethylation had occurred during sulphonation.

The sulphonation of 7-hydroxy-6-carbomethoxy-4-methylcoumarin with even one mole of chlorosulphonic acid at 60° was accompanied with the hydrolysis of the ester to the free carboxylic acid; lower temperatures also did not effect any sulphonation. The ester, when sulphonated with 1 mole of chlorosulphonic acid in chloroform medium, gave a monosulphonic acid of 7-hydroxy-6-carboxy-4-methylcoumarin along with some unchanged material. To determine the position of the sulphonic acid group in the latter, its bromination was carried out in acetic acid medium, when 7-hydroxy-3:8-dibromo-6-carboxy-4-methylcoumarin was obtained. On the basis of the observations made by Dalvi and Sethna (*loc. cit.*) (XX) was assigned the structure 7-hydroxy-6-carboxy-4-methylcoumarin-8-sulphonic acid.

The sulphonation of 7-hydroxy-6-carboxy-4-methylcoumarin took place with difficulty and was found to be incomplete with 1 mole of chlorosulphonic acid at 100°, whereas at higher temperatures charring occurred. With an excess of chlorosulphonic acid, only a disulphonic acid (XXI) could be obtained. The structure of the latter was determined by bromination, when the known 7-hydroxy-6-carboxy-3:8-dibromo-4-methylcoumarin resulted (Dalvi and Sethna, *loc. cit.*).

The sulphonation of the methyl ethers of 7-hydroxy-6-carboxy-4-methylcoumarin and its methyl ester was always accompanied with demethylation.

In the sulphonation of 7-hydroxycoumarin derivatives, the 6-position has been found to be the most reactive, the 8- and 3- positions being next in order of reactivity. The reactivity of the 6- position has also been observed in the nitration of 7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin where although a mixture of 6- and 8- isomers is obtained, the 6-nitro derivative is found to be in a greater yield (Pechmann and Obermiller, *Ber.*, 1901, 34, 666; Naik and Jadhav, this *Journal*, 1948, 25, 171). The latter authors also obtained the 8-nitro derivative by the nitration of 7-hydroxy-6-carbomethoxy-4-methylcoumarin.

In the bromination of 7-hydroxycoumarin derivatives Dalvi and Sethna (*loc. cit.*) observed that the first bromine atom entered the 3-position. By brominating 7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin, they obtained a greater of 3:6- than 3:8-dibromo derivative, showing that the 6-position was more reactive than '8'.

In case of 7-methoxycoumarin derivatives, the 6-position is the most reactive, the 3-position being next in order of reactivity. Nitration of 7-methoxy-4-methylcoumarin also gives the 6-nitro derivative first. Bromination of the above coumarin also affords the -3:6-dibromo compound. It is interesting to note that no sulphonation occurs in the 8-position in 7-methoxycoumarins without demethylation taking place at the same time. Demethylation of this methoxy group has also been observed by Dalvi and Sethna (*loc. cit.*) during bromination of 7-methoxy-6-carbomethoxy-4-methylcoumarin.

EXPERIMENTAL

All melting points are corrected. Freshly distilled chlorosulphonic acid was used for sulphonation. The products of sulphonation, their m.p. etc. are listed in Table II.

TABLE II
Derivatives of sulphonic acids and sulphonyl chlorides.

Sulphonation product	M.P.	Barium salt/ Sulphonyl chloride	Analysis.		S-Benzylisothiourea derivative/ anilide or amide.	M.P.	% Nitrogen.	
			Barium/Halogen. Found.	Calc.			Found.	Calc.
I	...	C ₁₈ H ₁₀ O ₁₁ S ₂ Ba	22.9	23.4	C ₁₇ H ₁₀ O ₅ N ₂ S ₂	212-14°	7.2	7.1
II	119-20°	C ₉ H ₅ O ₄ ClS	14.2	14.5	...	186°	...	...
III	...	C ₉ H ₅ O ₆ S ₂ Ba	31.0	31.1	C ₂₅ H ₁₆ O ₆ N ₂ S ₄	192-96°	8.9	8.8
IV	173-75°	C ₉ H ₅ O ₆ Cl ₂ S ₂	20.4	20.7	C ₉ H ₅ O ₆ N ₂ S ₂	>270°	9.2	9.2
V	...	C ₁₈ H ₈ O ₁₄ N ₂ S ₂ Ba	20.0	20.3	C ₁₇ H ₁₀ O ₆ N ₂ S ₂	218-20°	6.2	6.1
VI	204-205°	C ₉ H ₄ O ₆ NCIS	12.4	12.3	C ₁₇ H ₁₀ O ₇ N ₄ S ₂	230-32°	9.9	9.6
VII	...	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ O ₁₂ S ₂ Ba	21.2	21.2	C ₉ H ₅ O ₆ N ₂ S	>290°	9.9	10.4
VIII	178-80°	C ₁₆ H ₇ O ₃ ClS	12.6	12.9	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₆ N ₂ S	130°	7.7	8.1
IX	...	C ₁₀ H ₆ O ₃ S ₂ Ba	27.6	29.2	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₆ N ₂ S ₂	180-82°	7.0	6.6
X	...	C ₂₀ H ₁₀ O ₂₄ S ₄ Ba ₃	32.7	33.3	C ₁₈ H ₉ O ₅ NS	>290°	5.0	5.5
XI	...	...	...	...	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ O ₅ NS	245-47°	4.5	4.2
XII	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
XIII	210° (decomp.)	C ₁₀ H ₅ O ₃ Br ₂ ClS	7.6	7.4	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ O ₅ NBr ₂ S	210-12°	2.8	2.9
XIV	...	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ O ₁₂ S ₂ Ba	20.1	20.3	C ₁₈ H ₂₀ O ₆ N ₂ S ₂	250°	6.8	6.4
XV	203-204°	C ₁₁ H ₉ O ₃ ClS	12.4	12.3	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₅ NS	>310°	5.0	5.2
XVI	...	C ₁₁ H ₈ O ₉ S ₂ Ba	27.9	28.3	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ O ₅ NS	209-10°	4.1	4.1
XVII	230-32°	C ₁₁ H ₈ O ₇ Cl ₂ S ₂	18.5	18.35	C ₂₇ H ₃₀ O ₉ N ₄ S ₄	244°	8.1	8.2
XVIII	...	...	...	...	...	(decomp.)	...	...
XIX	227-29°	C ₁₁ H ₈ O ₃ ClBrS	8.5	8.7	C ₂₃ H ₂₀ O ₇ N ₂ S ₂	245-47°	5.75	5.6
XX	...	C ₂₂ H ₁₄ O ₁₆ S ₂ Ba	18.3	18.7	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ O ₆ N ₂ Br ₂ S ₂	280°	5.8	5.4
XXI	...	C ₁₁ H ₈ O ₁₁ S ₂ Ba	26.6	26.7	...	(decomp.)	...	...
					C ₁₇ H ₁₄ O ₅ NBrS	236-38°	3.6	3.3

The free sulphonic acid (XIV) gave crystals of m.p. 175° (decomp.) from concentrated hydrochloric acid (Found: S, 11.85. C₁₁H₁₀O₆S requires S, 11.5 %).

General Method for Sulphonation.—Chlorosulphonic acid was gradually added to the substance with cooling and the mixture, protected from moisture, was heated. After cooling, the contents were poured over crushed ice. The sulphonyl chlorides usually separated as pasty products which solidified on keeping. These were heated with ammonium carbonate or aniline to obtain the corresponding amides or anilides. The sulphonyl chlorides usually crystallised well from benzene or glacial acetic acid. The filtrate after removal of the sulphonyl chloride was saturated with sodium chloride, when the sodium salt of sulphonic acid separated in most cases. It was used as such for preparing the derivative with benzylisothiourea hydrochloride (prepared according to Chambers and Watts, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1941, 6, 376). The derivatives were usually crystallised from dilute alcohol. The barium salt of the sulphonic acid was either prepared from the purified sodium salt by double decomposition with barium chloride, or from the original mother-liquor after complete removal of hydrogen chloride and neutralising the concentrate with barium carbonate. The barium salts were recrystallised from water, dried at 130°-140° and immediately analysed.

Oxidation of Coumarin-6-sulphonic and -3:6-disulphonic Acids.—The sodium salts of the sulphonic acids were oxidised with potassium permanganate in alkaline medium, according to Sen and Chakravarti (*loc. cit.*). The potassium salt of the sulphonic acid

separating was used for the preparation of the derivative with benzylisothiurea hydrochloride. It was crystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 194-96°. (Found: N, 7.5. Calc. for $C_{15}H_{16}O_4N_2S_2$: N, 7.3%). Mixed m.p. with the derivative of 5-sulphosalicylic acid, prepared according to Meldrum and Shah (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 123, 1988), showed no lowering.

The oxidation of 6-nitrocoumarin-3-sulphonic acid was carried out in the same way as described above. The product was free from sulphur and was crystallised from hot water in needles, m.p. 227-28°. Mixed m.p. with 5-nitrosalicylic acid (Meldrum and Hirwe, this *Journal*, 1928, 5, 95) showed no lowering.

Bromination of 7-Hydroxy-4-methyl-6-sulphonic Acid (VII).—The sodium salt of the sulphonic acid (2 g.) was suspended in glacial acetic acid (8 c. c.) and a solution of bromine in acetic acid (10% ; 12 c.c., 1 M) was added to it with shaking. The mixture was kept at room temperature for five hours and filtered into water. The precipitate obtained was crystallised from acetic acid in white shining plates, m.p. 250-52°. (Found: Br, 57.8. Calc. for $C_{10}H_8O_3Br_3$: Br, 58.1%). Mixed m.p. with an authentic specimen of 7-hydroxy-3:6:8-tribromo-4-methylcoumarin (Dalvi and Sethna, *loc. cit.*) showed no lowering.

The same tribromo derivative was obtained by bromination of the sodium salts of 7-hydroxy-3:6-dibromo-4-methylcoumarin-8-sulphonic acid and 7-hydroxy-3:8-dibromo-4-methylcoumarin-6-sulphonic acid with an excess of bromine in acetic acid medium at 100°.

Bromination of 7-Hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin-6-sulphonyl Chloride (VIII).—The sulphonyl chloride (1 g.) was dissolved in glacial acetic acid (10 c.c.) by boiling and a solution of bromine in acetic acid (10% ; 11 c.c., 2M) was added gradually to the hot solution with shaking. After 6 hours at room temperature, the crystals of the bromo compound were filtered and recrystallised from acetic acid in white needles, m.p. 208-10° (decomp.). (Found: S, 7.6. Calc. for $C_{10}H_7O_3ClBr_2S$: S, 7.4%). Its mixed m.p. with the sulphonyl chloride obtained by the sulphonation of 7-hydroxy-3:8-dibromo-4-methylcoumarin showed no lowering.

Bromination of 7-Methoxy-4-methylcoumarin-6-sulphonic Acid (XIV).—The sodium salt (1 g.) was brominated with 2 moles of bromine in acetic acid medium. After heating on the water-bath for 15 minutes, the mixture was poured into water. The white precipitate obtained was crystallised from acetic acid in needles, m.p. 240°. Its mixed m.p. with 7-methoxy-3:6-dibromo-4-methylcoumarin (Dalvi and Sethna, *loc. cit.*) showed no lowering.

Bromination of 7-Methoxycoumarin-6-sulphonyl Chloride (XV).—The sulphonyl chloride was brominated as before with 2 moles of bromine in acetic acid. Crystallisation furnished white needles, m.p. 227-28°. (Found: S, 8.5. $C_{11}H_9O_3ClBrS$ requires S, 8.7%).

Oxidation of 7-Methoxy-4-methylcoumarin-6-sodium sulphonate.—The substance (5 g.) was dissolved in 2N-KOH (75 c.c.) and a 4% solution of $KMnO_4$ (200 c.c.) was added dropwise with stirring. After heating on the water-bath for one hour, the mixture was filtered, acidified and concentrated to a small bulk. The product separating was used for the preparation of the barium salt and for the derivative with benzylisothiurea

hydrochloride, which crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 228-30° (decomp.). (Found : N, 7.1. $C_{16}H_{16}O_7N_2S_2$ requires N, 6.8%). (Found : Ba, 21.7. $C_{16}H_{16}O_{14}S_2Ba$ requires Ba, 21.8%). Mixed m.p. with the derivative of 2-hydroxy-4-methoxy-5-sulphobenzoic acid showed no depression.

The free sulphonic acid obtained by decomposition of the barium salt was crystallised from HCl (conc.) in green needles, m.p. 175-78° (decomp.). It was dried at 100° under vacuum and analysed. (Found : S, 13.5. Calc. for $C_8H_8O_7S$: S, 12.9%).

2-Hydroxy-4-methoxy-5-sulphobenzoic Acid.—2-Hydroxy-4-methoxybenzoic acid (5 g.) (prepared according to Gomberg and Johnson, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1917, 39, 1687) was heated with H_2SO_4 (conc., 25 g.) at 100° for 2 hours and then poured into brine when the sodium salt precipitated. It was used for preparing the derivative with benzylisothiurea hydrochloride, which crystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 230-32° (decomp.). Senhöfer and Brünner (*Chem. Zentr.*, 1879, I, 566) sulphonated β -resorcylic acid and obtained a sulphonic acid to which they assigned the structure 2:4-dihydroxy-5(?)sulphobenzoic acid. The position of the sulphonic acid group in the latter was confirmed by its methylation to 2-hydroxy-4-methoxy-5-sulphobenzoic acid obtained above. The S-benzylisothiuronium derivative of 2:4-dihydroxy-5-sulphobenzoic acid was crystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 201-202°. (Found : N, 7.4. $C_{15}H_{14}O_7N_2S_2$ requires N, 7.0%).

Bromination of 2-Hydroxy-4-methoxy-5-sulphobenzoic Acid.—The sodium salt (2 g.) was brominated with a solution of bromine in acetic acid (10%, 12 c.c.). The mixture was heated on the water-bath for 10 minutes and poured into water. The precipitate obtained was crystallised from alcohol in white needles, m.p. 251-52°. (Found : Br, 32.5. Calc. for $C_8H_7O_4Br$: Br, 32.4%).

The same bromo compound was obtained by bromination of 2-hydroxy-4-methoxybenzoic acid. The structure of the bromo compound as 2-hydroxy-4-methoxy-5-bromobenzoic acid was confirmed by preparing its methyl ester, m.p. 143° (Rice, *loc. cit.*, records m.p. 143°) and by decarboxylating it to 4-bromoresorcinol-3-methyl ether, m.p. 83-84° (lit. m.p. 84°).

Bromination of 7-Methoxy-4-methylcoumarin-3:6-disodium disulphonate (XVI).—The bromination was carried out as usual with 3 moles of bromine in acetic acid. The product obtained after crystallisation from acetic acid had m.p. 240°. Its mixed m.p. with an authentic sample of 7-methoxy-3:6-dibromo-4-methylcoumarin (Dalvi and Sethna, *loc. cit.*) showed no depression.

Bromination of 7-Hydroxy-6-carboxy-4-methylcoumarin-8-sodium sulphonate.—The substance (1 g.) was suspended in acetic acid (10 c.c.) and a solution of bromine in acetic acid (10% ; 6 c.c.) was added. The reaction mixture was boiled under reflux for 2 hours and poured into water. The product which had separated was crystallised from acetic acid in needles, m.p. 284-86° (decomp.). Its mixed m.p. with an authentic specimen of 7-hydroxy-6-carboxy-3:8-dibromo-4-methylcoumarin (Dalvi and Sethna, *loc. cit.*) showed no lowering. The same dibromo compound was obtained by bromination of 7-hydroxy-6-carboxy-4-methylcoumarin-3:8-disodium disulphonate under identical conditions.